

Composite Flywheel Rotor Containment

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ABSTRACT

Composite construction has been increasingly applied to the development of efficient flywheel rotors for vehicular energy storage systems. New developments in understanding and quantifying composite rotor burst containment behavior are contributing to advancing the practicality of such systems. The paper briefly discusses some of these developments, summarizes overall design requirements for containment housings, and presents a novel analysis of composite rotor containment action. The analysis considers fragmentation released from a failed composite rotor as undergoing a progressive crushing process during containment. The process is characterized by a constant parameter called the apparent fragment crushing strength, which is the ability of initially released fragmentation to resist progressive breakdown under the applied containment forces. The analysis has been successfully applied to correlating the containment test behavior of a variety of high performance composite rotors. Burst-containment weight estimates based on the analysis are also presented for several containment ring constructions. Containment considerations for a loose rotor spinning on the housing interior are also discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Considerable research and development work has been directed during the past seven years to exploiting the large potential of flywheel energy storage systems (1-4). These activities have been spurred by the energy crisis and particular attention has been focused on the consumer passenger vehicle applications since these offer the greatest promise of reducing conventional fuel consumption on a world scale. In the United States, flywheel R&D programs have been largely sponsored by the Department of Energy (DOE), through which the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) has played a principal role in directing and coordinating them. Under the Mechanical Energy Storage Technology (MEST) Project major advances have been achieved in composite flywheel rotor design and fabrication technologies and a significant start in developing burst-containment design capability. A wide assortment of composite rotors featuring a variety of constructions and materials has been produced during this effort. Table 1 lists some of these and identifies three generic rotor design categories, namely, rim, disk, and rim/disk hybrid types. In burst tests several rotors have demonstrated energy densities that approach current DOE goals for vehicular flywheel systems

(40 wh/lb): 36.1 and 30.5 wh/lb (Garrett AiResearch and LLNL respectively) and 3050 and 2280 wh/ft³ (LLNL and General Electric Company respectively). Also, composite rotor burst and containment processes for a variety of rotor constructions are now better understood as a result of detailed studies of spin test data, and this has led to definition of containment housing conceptual designs (5,6).

An outstanding advantage of a flywheel for energy storage is its high specific peak power (more than 500 W/kg). As indicated in Figure 1 this means that it can supply sudden power demands (and absorb sudden power inputs) better than conventional storage batteries. Hence the flywheel could be particularly useful in applications involving sudden drains from a power source that works best under a constant power demand (stop-and-go driving, for example), or for coupling a varying load to an intermittent power source such as wind or solar power.

Studies have shown that an automobile equipped with a flywheel system could have up to twice the urban mileage rating of a conventional car of similar size and performance. Doubling the efficiency of all urban vehicles in this country, i.e., replacing them all with flywheel-equipped vehicles, could result in substantial energy savings.

The other outstanding potential application of flywheel energy storage is in matching the intermittent output of such alternative energy sources as wind and solar power to the demands of energy consumers. A windmill's power varies as the cube of wind speed. Therefore, even for relatively steady winds, there is a tremendous fluctuation in power output. A flywheel generator system could absorb these bursts of power and maintain a steady output.

Similarly, solar collectors gather power only by day. Some form of energy storage is essential to cover nighttime energy needs. A large flywheel installation could be a relatively compact system for accomplishing this.

Composite flywheels, because of their high momentum-to-weight ratio, are used in many spacecraft for attitude control. Spaceborne energy-storage applications are also under development to supply sudden bursts of power.

Flywheels made of composite materials look quite promising when compared with the drawbacks of conventionally designed steel flywheels. Steel flywheels have definite, well-known limitations that have inhibited the further development of flywheel energy storage. For example, they are markedly heavier for passenger-car or load-leveling service, although experimental diesel buses using steel flywheels for energy storage are in the prototype development stage in several European countries.

Composite materials, on the other hand, have a higher specific strength than steel, and flywheels made from them can store two to three times as much energy per kilogram as steel flywheels. A prototype trolley bus driven by a composite-material flywheel is under development in the U.S. (Garrett AiResearch) and various cities across the country have expressed interest in its potential.

In addition to obtaining high energy-density, composite has been preferred over metallic rotor construction because of the relatively benign containment processes that are associated with rotor burst. In the early stages of the MEST Project, this awareness was based principally on observation of post-burst debris which showed that composite rotors fragment to a much higher degree than metallic rotors and indicated a much lower capability to inflict damage to a containment housing. Much experience, however, was available with metallic rotor bursts which showed very severe containment processes. Estimates of containment weight requirements for metallic rotors often indicated values several times greater than the rotor weight itself. Although metallic flywheel rotors that are designed to release relatively low damage-potential fragmentation upon failure have been produced (7), such approaches have not been emphasized in major MEST project developments that have aimed at transportation vehicle applications.

Instead, composite construction has been favored because of the promise of higher energy density and intrinsically safer containment.

Early assessments of composite-rotor containment processes led some to underestimate the need for substantial containment devices. Tests performed (8) during the past two years, however, have shown that composite-rotor bursts can produce impressive amounts of damage in heavy containment structures, although the damage is still well below that produced by a comparable metallic rotor burst. The optimum system will most likely incorporate rotor and containment housing designs which offer the best combination of performance indices (energy density, durability, and cost). It may possibly employ a less than optimum rotor if its containment requirements are sufficiently lower than those of the optimum one.

Containment is therefore a strong driver in developing an efficient vehicular flywheel system, and the next logical step is to demonstrate the safe containment of candidate rotors in realistic housings. Such an accomplishment will greatly strengthen the case for flywheel systems in transportation vehicles. For basically, containment is a safety issue whose time for resolution has come.

This paper describes some recent advances that have been made in understanding and quantifying the containment behavior of composite rotors and estimating containment requirements for transportation vehicle applications.

CONTAINMENT HOUSING DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

Design requirements for flywheel containment housings can be divided into two categories, one that relates to a possible rotor failure event and the other to functional operation of the system.

A. Rotor Failure Requirements

1. Containment of Rotor Burst
2. Debris Management
3. Loose Rotor Control
4. Limitation of Reactions Transferred to the Vehicle

B. Operational Requirements

1. Vacuum Support
2. Structural Integrity
3. Noise Suppression
4. Safe Response to Vehicle Collision

Category B requirements can be addressed using existing design technology. Briefly, in the order listed, the housing must support the required internal vacuum and permit convenient assembly and maintenance procedures. This requires mechanically fastened housing joints that incorporate elastomeric gas seals. Because of this a vacuum pumping system will be required to maintain the internal housing pressure at values sufficiently low to limit aerodynamic heating of the rotor throughout its operating speed range. Vacuum pressure levels may have to be as low as 5×10^{-3} torr for low temperature composite rotors (9). Vacuum pump requirements and selection are also discussed in (9).

The principal static load on the housing structure is due to the external atmospheric pressure, which turns out to be a chief contributor to housing weight for the single rotor designs anticipated for small transportation vehicles.

The housing and its attachment to the vehicle, as well as the rotor and its support, must be sufficiently rugged to withstand shocks that may be transmitted in a survivable vehicle collision. If the housing is not subject to direct impact by hard objects during collision, the flywheel system can be expected to tolerate the imposed g-forces.

Since a light-weight flywheel housing can be an effective radiator of sound, noise suppression techniques must be input to the design process. This may involve reducing noise in associated bearings or gears or incorporating sound absorbing materials in the housing walls (10).

Category A requirements present a greater technical challenge, since little experience exists with composite rotor containment in realistic flywheel housings. Burst-containment processes for composite rotors of various constructions were studied recently and an analysis of containment behavior developed (5). This has been applied to determine containment ring dimensions and to evaluate advanced containment design concepts. Less is known about how to accommodate the large volume of fragments and debris that is usually generated following composite rotor burst. A major design goal is to preclude local build-up and compaction of debris and resulting wedging actions by proper housing design.

The housing must also handle a loose rotor condition that can occur in the possible event of rotor break-away from the shaft. It is important to preclude transmission of disturbing levels of resulting reaction forces and torques from the housing to the vehicle. This can be accomplished by permitting the housing to rotate relative to the vehicle attachment joints, once a specified attachment torque threshold has been exceeded. Such a technique limits loose-rotor type reaction forces as well as the torques produced by loose rotor and rotor burst actions.

CONTAINMENT ANALYSIS AND TEST CORRELATION

Results of burst tests of composite rotors which had been performed at the Johns Hopkins U. Applied Physics Laboratory (APL) (8) were studied. The tests, listed in Table 1, involved a variety of rotor materials, constructions, and failure modes. The test results were especially useful because the rotors released a substantial and defined amount of fragmentation within the containment rings that were not excessively massive. Consequently, the rings were substantially deformed in the more severe bursts, while in the less severe ones, the rings, although not detectably deformed, nevertheless permitted deduction of an upper bound of containment severity. The tests provided a data base which helped in the development of the containment analysis.

When interacting with a containment ring, metallic fragments due to their material isotropy can exert contact pressures that exceed their yield stress. Also because of their high toughness, they typically remain intact during the entire process, thereby maintaining high bearing and shearing pressures. In contrast, composite fragments because of their relatively low transverse and interlaminar strengths cannot exert such high pressures. When pressures induced in the fragment exceed these strength limits, the matrix can be expected to break up, thereby releasing fibers or ribbons of fibers (filament-wound construction) or local delamination and crushing (laminated construction, edge loading). Rapid heating at the fragment/ring interface due to high pressure, high speed sliding also contributes to rapid fragment break-up. In some constructions, the initially released fragments may already be in a highly broken state prior to engagement.

Since the fragments are basically solid, as opposed to porous, bodies, such action may be accompanied by the forcible ejection of material laterally from the fragment as the remaining fragment moves radially toward the containment structure. If the transverse strength is low, the fragment may continue this motion until its mass is expended. If the strength is high, however, the ejected mass may be appropriately less and a substantial portion of the original fragment remains after its radial velocity relative to the containment surface has vanished. Such residual fragments may continue to move tangentially after this time and exert centrifugal pressures against the containment ring.

An analysis, called the crushing fragment containment analysis (CFCA) was developed to calculate the containment ring response to such a loading process and is described in detail in (5). Only a brief account is given here to provide

a basis for describing the calculated results. The analysis assumes that at failure the rotor releases an axially symmetric distribution of fragments which contacts the containment ring after moving through the radial clearance space that initially exists between the rotor and ring. Subsequently, the fragment system is further assumed to undergo a continuous radial crushing process, provided that the applied containment pressure exceeds a parameter p_0 , called the apparent fragment crushing strength. Whenever the applied pressure is less than p_0 , the fragment system remains rigid. During crushing, the fragment system ejects material from its lateral (axial) faces. In the usual case, the fragment system crushes initially and finally attains a rigid state with reduced mass and radial thickness (residual fragment system). Throughout the process the containment ring is free to expand radially and will do so when the applied containment pressure exceeds its dynamic tensile strength or when it is finally coasting to rest. The containment is considered adequate when the final radial growth of the ring is within allowable limits.

The interaction geometry is illustrated in Figure 2 which shows how the fragment proceeds to move into the ring. The initial state of the fragment is indicated by its bounding radii R_I and r_{I1} , thickness a_I , and centroid position, r_{I1} . The initial total, radial and angular velocities are V_0 , \dot{r}_I , and ω_I respectively. These same quantities apply everywhere around the circumference since the fragmentation geometry and motion are considered to be axially symmetric. The various dashed lines indicate the trajectories of the fragment inner surface and mass center and the containment ring as time progresses. At a general instant, the fragment thickness is shown as having a centroidal radius, r , thickness, a , angular speed, ω , and total and radial speeds V and \dot{r} . It is noted that although V is always less than V_0 , the radial speed may increase above the initial radial speed for a while. The final state of the fragment is depicted by the residual thickness, a_p , at the point where its radial velocity equilibrates with that of the containment ring.

The motion of the entire fragment is therefore characterized by that of the general mass center, m , whose variable mass per unit circumference $2\pi r$ is:

$$m = 2 \rho_F h(R-r), \quad (1)$$

where ρ_F is the distributed fragment density. The equations of motion of the fragment and containment ring (neglecting friction) are:

$$\text{Fragment: } \ddot{r} + \left(\frac{\dot{R} - \dot{r}}{m} \right) \dot{m} = \frac{H^2}{r^3} - \frac{p_0 h}{m} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Ring: } \ddot{R} = \frac{2\pi}{M_C} \left[(\dot{R} - \dot{r}) \dot{m} r + p_0 h r - \sigma T_e L_e \right] \quad (3)$$

where the single and double dots indicate first and second time derivations respectively; $H = \omega r^2 = \text{constant}$, p_0 , fragment crushing strength; h , rotor axial length; σ , dynamic tensile strength of ring; T_e , ring thickness; and M_C and L_e , the effective mass and length of the ring. Hence, the fragment is treated as a variable mass which transfers momentum loads, $(\dot{R} - \dot{r})\dot{m}$ and pressure loads, $p_0 h$ (both per unit circumference) to the containment ring. The ring resists these loads by its plastic tensile resistance $\sigma T_e L_e$.

The initial conditions are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fragment: } r(0) &= r_I, \quad \dot{r}(0) = V_{R_I} \\ \text{Ring: } R(0) &= R_I, \quad \dot{R}(0) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

During the ensuing process, the condition $\dot{r} = \dot{R} = V_{Rp}$ is reached, at which time and thereafter, the fragment is considered to be rigid. Subsequently, the fragment continues moving circumferentially at angular velocity ω_p and exerting centrifugal pressure loading on the ring:

$$p_p = \frac{m_p (\omega_p r_p)^2}{R_p h} \quad (5)$$

During this time the radial motion of fragment and ring is governed by:

$$\ddot{R} = \frac{2\pi}{(M_c + M_p)} \left[p_p h r_p - \sigma T_e L_e \right] \quad (6)$$

where $M_p = 2 \pi r_p m_p$.

For present purposes, equation (6) was solved assuming the bracket term to be constant. Although not necessary to do this, it is conservative and it was convenient to do so. Hence the final time at which the radial velocity ceases is:

$$t_f = t_p + \frac{M_c + M_p}{2\pi} \left[\frac{V_{Rp}}{\sigma T_e L_e - p_p h r_p} \right] \quad (7)$$

and the maximum radial deflection of the ring:

$$\Delta R_{max} = R_p - R_I + \frac{1}{2} V_{Rp} (t_f - t_p)$$

CFCA has yielded some very interesting features of containment processes of composite rotors, features which appear plausible, especially when compared with experimental evidence of fragmentation as obtained for rotors of various constructions. The following results illustrate some of these features.

Figures 3 and 4 show plots of r , \dot{r} , R , and \dot{R} vs. time for the complete burst of a 0.25 kw.hr laminated glass/epoxy disk rotor, the principal differences being the fragment strength and ring thickness values: $p_0 = 0$ and $T = 0.22$ in. (Figure 3) and $p_0 = 12$ ksi and $T = 0.35$ in. (Figure 4). In each case, $\dot{r} = 387$ in/sec. initially (which corresponds to an initial radial clearance, $c = 0.25$ in.) and subsequently rises to a peak value. The peak value of r is larger for $p_0 = 0$ and occurs at a later time than for $p_0 = 12$ ksi. Also, r approaches closer to R for $p_0 = 0$ such that at the equilibration condition, $\dot{r} = \dot{R} = V_{Rp}$, the residual fragment thickness ($a = 2(R-4)$) is much smaller than that of the stronger fragment. This is typical of fragment behavior as revealed by CFCA. It is noted that even though $p_0 = 0$, substantial deformation is produced in the ring. This, of course, is attributable to the fragment momentum loading.

Another interesting result is to show that fragments having low strength can transmit substantial deformation to the ring even when the initial radial clearance is zero. An example is illustrated in Figure 5, which pertains to the same conditions as the previous Figures except $p_0 = 6$ ksi, $T = 0.24$ in., and $c = 0$. Here \dot{r} is initially zero, (because of the zero clearance) but rises to a peak value of 4,870 in/sec. \dot{R} remains at zero for the first 200 μ sec. and rises thereafter to a peak value of 1,570 in/sec., almost as high as for the case shown in Figure 3. The maximum ring deflection, $\Delta R = 0.62$ in., compared to 0.60 in. (Figure 3). Since for these two cases, the ring thicknesses, T , are almost identical, it is seen that the effect of the higher fragment strength tends to be offset by the smaller clearance value.

The CFCA was successfully used to analyze the containment behavior of a variety of rotor types. When applied to the APL tests, it permitted evaluation of p_0 for the laminated glass/epoxy disk, laminated graphite/epoxy disk, and chopped glass SMC molded disk rotors and filament-wound graphite/epoxy and Kevlar[®]

49/epoxy rings. The resulting values of p_0 which are dependent on the composite material and construction and the radial impact speed are shown in Table 2 along with other test data such as radial clearance, C, and radial fragment speed at initial contact, V_R . It is noted that these values of p_0 were obtained in open-ended containment rings and at much larger values of V_R than representative of practical applications. Fragment actions occurring within the more confined clearance spaces of practical flywheel housings are expected to involve values of p_0 that may differ from those listed in Table 2. Confinement, for example, would tend to produce higher than listed values of p_0 by inhibiting the axial ejection of fragment debris. This is especially pertinent to fragmentation associated with low (listed) values of p_0 .

BURST-CONTAINMENT REQUIREMENTS

Containment ring weights W_C , as obtained from CFCA for a .25 kwh, 18 in. OD, 28.9 lb laminated glass/epoxy disk rotor are shown in Figure 6 for several ring materials. These estimates are based on $p_0 = 6$ ksi (rather than $p_0 = 0$ as listed in Table 3), a conservative value which was used to account for possible effects of fragment compaction in the relatively confined clearance spaces of practical flywheel housings. W_C is shown plotted against the maximum radial growth. The dots on the curves show the maximum allowable ring growth, which corresponds to 10 percent tensile strain except for the four percent value of Kevlar® 29/6061 Al ring. This latter construction employs a metallic liner overwound by aramid yarn and is promising for weight-critical applications (25% of rotor weight). The 4130 steel ring appears to be a desirable choice for transportation vehicle applications (50% of rotor weight) which are more constrained by cost. The plot also indicates that designs with very small growth may be obtained by employing moderately heavier rings. Such designs may be advantageous where the additional weight can be allowed.

LOOSE-ROTOR REQUIREMENTS

Reactions transmitted to the housing by a loose rotor spinning against it were calculated for three conditions, (1) fixed housing, (2) unrestrained housing, and (3) unrestrained containment ring. Figure 7 shows a plot of transmitted reaction force and torque vs. radial operating clearance. This applies to the same rotor as stated in Figure 6. It is seen that the reactions are especially sensitive to the clearance and, for large clearances, also to the housing restraint. The reactions are greatest when the housing is fixed and smallest when the containment ring is unrestrained. In a practical design, both the ring and housing will be at least partially restrained from rotation and the reactions actually obtained will be higher than shown for the unrestrained conditions. Since the running clearances of .25 kwh rotors will likely be less than .25 in. or several percent of rotor outside radius, tolerable reactions are indicated irrespective of the restraint condition. This applies strictly to the torque reaction of a laminated glass/epoxy rotor and a steel containment ring because the friction (coefficient ($\mu=.11$)) used in the analysis was obtained from a loose rotor test (8) that involved such components. The magnitude of the force reaction, however, does not appear to be dependent on the friction coefficient and therefore should apply to components made of other materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The developments described above indicate that burst-containment requirements for composite rotors can be determined following a rational design procedure involving the following steps: (1) Definition of the rotor failure modes based on composite strength analysis; (2) Computation of containment ring dimensions vs. ring growth, based on rotor failure modes and given material and operational properties, using an analysis such as described herein; and (3) Selection of a specific ring design (ring thickness, growth, material) that satisfies such constraints as integration into the overall housing design and rotor/housing system weight, volume, and cost.

The basis for the overall housing design is less well established at present due to very limited experience with composite rotor containment in realistic housings. A conceptual housing design described in (5) incorporates features aimed at adequate debris management, resistance to axial fragment-induced loads, and limitation of reactions transferred to the vehicle; but such processes are not well understood. The next step to developing an adequate containment housing design practice is, therefore, to perform containment tests in realistic housings, employing candidate composite flywheel rotors, and ultimately translate resulting test data into design requirements.

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Table 1. Description of Flywheel Rotors Involved in the Data Correlation

Rotor Description	d_o in.	W_R lb.	KE_B kwh	ω_B rpm	Failure Mode	W_F lb.
Hybrid Rotor: FW Graphite/Epoxy Ring; Laminated S-2 Glass/Epoxy Disk (General Electric)	17.68	23.3	0.459	35,040	Outer ring Rupture	6.34
Disk Rotor: Laminates D-2 Glass/Epoxy Disk (LLNL)	15.00	5.2	0.156	49,320	Complete Disk Burst	5.2
Hybrid Rotor: FW Graphite/Epoxy Outer Ring; Molded Chopped Glass/SMC Disk (Owens Corning)	24.00	28.5	0.414	21,620	Complete Burst of Rim and Disk	28.5
Wound-Rim Rotor: FW Kevlar 49/Epoxy, Glass/Epoxy (Brobeck)	13.76	24.5	0.608	48,120	Rupture of 70% of Kevlar 49/Epoxy Rim	6.76
Disk Rotor: Varying Thickness, Laminated Graphite/Epoxy	24.00	11.8	0.306	34,940	Complete Disk Burst	11.8

d_o , OD, W_R , rotor weight; KE_B , energy at burst, ω_B , burst speed, W_F , total fragment weight.

Table 2. Values of p_0 , Fragment Crushing Strength as Obtained from Data Analysis of APL Flywheel Rotor Burst Tests

Material	Form	Impact Direction	p_0 (psi)	C (in.)	V_R (in/sec)
Graphite/Epoxy	Filament Wound Ring	Transverse	20,000	4.62	22,900
	Laminate	Longitudinal	45,000	1.50	15,790
S-2 Glass/Epoxy	Laminate	Longitudinal	0	1.50	16,470
Kevlar 49/Epoxy	Filament Wound Ring	Transverse	0	2.12	21,540
Chopped Glass/SMC	Molding	Longitudinal	5,000	1.50	9,880

Figure 1. Performance Comparison of Various Energy Storage Systems

Figure 3. Calculated Fragment and Containment Ring Motions vs. Time for Complete Burst of a 0.25 kwh Laminated Glass/Epoxy Disk Rotor. $p_0 = 0$; 4130 Steel Ring ($\sigma = 158$ ksi).

Figure 2. Crushing Fragment Interaction Schematic

Figure 4. Calculated Fragment and Containment Ring Motions vs. Time for Complete Burst of a .25 kwh Laminated S-Glass/Epoxy Disk Rotor. $p_0 = 12,000$ psi; 4130 Steel Ring ($\sigma = 158$ ksi)

Figure 5. Calculated Fragment and Containment Ring Motions vs. Time for Complete Burst of a 0.25 kwh Laminated S-Glass/Epoxy Disk Rotor. $p_0 = 6,000$ psi. Radial Clearance, $C = 0$; 4130 Steel Ring ($\sigma = 158$ ksi)

Figure 6. Containment Design Curves: W_c vs. ΔR_{max} for Complete Burst of an 18 in. OD, 0.25 kwh Laminated S-Glass/Epoxy Disk Rotor for Several Containment Ring Materials

Figure 7. Loose Rotor Induced Force and Torque Reactions Transmitted to the Vehicle for Various Housing Fixity Conditions vs. Running Clearance, Based on 18 in. OD Laminated S-Glass/Epoxy Disk Rotor